

COMPRESSION BEHAVIOR OF CONCRETE CYLINDERS EXTERNALLY CONFINED BY FLAX FIBER REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In this article, natural flax fibers or hybrid of flax and basalt fibers was used to confine concrete cylinders. Mechanical properties of the FRPs and the compression performances of the confined cylinders were investigated. For comparison, unidirectional basalt fiber fabric reinforced polymer confined cylinders were also tested. FFRP plates exhibit a nonlinear tensile stress-strain response, which is contrast to BFRP and HFRP. Hybrid of flax fibers with basalt fibers brings in increased tensile properties compared to FFRP. FFRP tubes confines the concrete cylinders effectively, leading to a remarkable enhancement of the compressive stress and strain. Thee confinement effectiveness of the FFRP and HFRP tubes are greater than that of BFRP.

1 INTRODUCTION

As alternatives to glass or carbon fibers, natural fibers have been accepted as fiber reinforcements for FRP (fiber reinforced polymer) composites. The specific properties of the natural fibres (e.g., flax, sisal, ramie, etc.) namely low cost, lightweight, renewable character, carbon dioxide sequestration, biodegradability, high specific strength and modulus, availability in a variety of forms throughout the world, surface reactivity and the possibility to generate energy, absence of associated health hazards, easy fibre surface modification, and relative non-abrasiveness encourages the incorporation of them with polymers to synthesize composites with desired qualities [1].

Besides of the application of the natural fiber based FRPs in automobile, decoration and others, natural fiber FRPs have found acceptance in civil engineering in recent years [2, 3]. In our group, a bi-directional flax fiber fabric with room temperature curable epoxy was used to confine concrete cylinders. The compressive test results of confined concrete cylinders indicate that FFRPs improved the ultimate strain and stress of the confined cylinders, remarkably. The coefficients of confinement of FFRP on the ultimate compression stress are slightly higher than that of BFRP. The confined cylinders with FFRP showed much higher ultimate axial strain than those with BFRP [3]. Flax FRP tubes were used confine concrete cylinders [4], and the experimental result is compared with the existing glass/carbon FRP (G/CFRP) confined concrete regarding to confinement effectiveness. It shows that the confinement effectiveness of the proposed cylinders is close to or comparable to the G/CFRP confined concrete. This is true despite the tensile strength of FFRP composite, as obtained from flat coupon tensile testing, being significant lower than that of G/CFRP.

In the current study, tubes were prepared with winding process with unidirectional flax fiber, and flax-basalt hybrid fibers. The tubes were applied to confine pure concrete, and the compression performances of the confined concrete cylinders were tested. The effectiveness of confinement by flax

fiber and hybrid fibers were compared. The study will demonstrate the feasibility of the natural fiber reinforced FRPs used in structural strengthening rehabilitation and upgrading.

2 EXPERIMENTALS

2.1 Raw materials

The flax yarn was purchased from Harbin Linen Textile Co., Ltd (Harbin, China). The average linear density is 0.039g/m. The count is 15 Ne in English cotton count. The tensile strength, modulus and elongation at break of the single flax fiber are 750MPa, 35GPa and 1.2%, respectively.

The continuous and untwisted basalt fiber roving was provided by the Tuo Xin Aerospace Basalt Industrial Co., Ltd. (Chengdu, China). The average diameter of the basalt fiber is 13.5 μm . The density of the basalt fiber is 2.65 g/cm^3 . The tensile strength, modulus and elongation at break of the single basalt fiber are 2.7GPa, 85.4GPa and 3.7%, respectively.

The resin used in the present study is diglycidyl ether of bisphenol-F (DGEBF) epoxy with the brand name of NPEF-170 (Nan Ya Plastic Corporation, New Taipei, China). Methyl hexahydrophthalic anhydride (MHHPA) was used as a hardener, which was produced by Qing Yang Chemistry Co., Ltd (Jiaying, China).

2.2 Preparation and mechanical test of FRP plates and tubes

Three kinds of FRPs were fabricated with a fiber winding process in the present study. The designation and compositions of the FRPs plates and tubes are presented in Table 1 & 2, respectively. The FFRP (flax fiber reinforced polymer), BFRP (basalt fiber reinforced polymer) and HFRP (flax and basalt hybrid fibers reinforced polymer) plates and tubes were prepared by a winding machine (4FW500 \times 2000, Harbin Composite Equipment Co., Harbin, China). The winding speed was set as 0.15mm/s, and the winding angle for plates and tubes was 89.2 for basalt fibers and 89.6 for flax fibers respectively. The prepared plates or tubes were considered as unidirectional. The winding interval for basalt fiber is 3.5mm and 0.04mm for flax yarn. The nominal thickness of flax layer and basalt fiber layer are 0.104mm and 0.29mm.

Designation	Description	Measured thickness (mm)	Fiber content (vol.%)
FFRP	12 flax layers	2.55	49.2
BFRP	3 basalt layers	1.53	57.7
HFRP	1 basalt layer + 8 flax layer + 1 basalt layer	2.83	50.4

Table 1: Designation and compositions of FFRP, BFRP and HFRP plates and tubes.

The wound FFRP plate and tubes were cured in an oven at 120 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for one hour, and then 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for another hour. The plates and tubes were demolded after fully cooling down of the samples. The photographs of the prepared FFRP plate and tube are shown in Fig. 1.

Designation	Description	Measured thickness (mm)	Fiber content (vol.%)
FFRP	8 flax layers	2.49	33.6
BFRP	2 basalt layers	1.72	34.2
HFRP	1 basalt layer +8 flax layer + 1 basalt layer	4.42	34.5

Table 2: The designation and properties of FRP tubes.

In the present study, three concrete filled tubes were tested in the axial compressive behaviors. The

designation and properties of FRP tubes are shown in Table 2. To avoid water ingress into the FFRP composite, after the fabrication of the tubes, one layer of waterproof resin was uniformly coated inside the tubes.

Figure 1: Prepared FFRP plate and tube.

2.3 Preparation and compression test of concrete cylinders

Self-compacting concrete (SCC) with the design strength of 30MPa was casted in the tubes and cured for 28 days in the laboratory before test. The ends of the SCC filled FRP tubes were confined with 30mm CFRP strips to avoid end damage of the cylinders during compression test.

The cylinders are tested in 500T hydraulically operated machine (YNS-Y, Changchun Research Institute for Mechanical Science Co., Changchun, China) with the load speed of 0.25MPa/s. The axial strain was measured by four LVDTs (linear voltage differential transducers). Total 8 strain gauges were attached equally in the middle of the cylinder, 4 of them are for axial strain and 4 for hoop. The samples for measurement are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Test setup and instrumentation details.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Properties of FFRP plates

The tensile stress-strain curves of FFRP, BFRP and HFRP are shown in Fig. 3. The tensile curve of FFRP is nonlinear, the elastic modulus decreases with the increase of the tensile strain, while BFRP shows almost linear in the stress-strain curve. The tensile curve of HFRP is located between the tensile curves of FFRP and BFRP.

Figure 3: The tensile stress-strain curve of FRP plates.

The tensile results of those three FRPs are summarized in Table 3. Note, the tensile strength and elastic modulus are calculated with the nominal thickness of the composed fibers. The elastic modulus of FFRP and HFRP are calculated with the strain from the starting point to 0.2%.

	Tensile strength, f_{frp} (MPa)	Elastic modulus, E_{frp} (GPa)	Elongation at break, ε_{frp} (%)
FFRP	333.0	48.5	1.28
BFRP	994.6	65.7	1.58
HFRP	613.1	54.9	1.44

Table 3: The tensile properties of FFRP, BFRP and HFRP plates.

To evaluate the contribution of each type of fiber in HFRP, the tensile properties of HFRP coupon can be calculated with the role of mixture. The tensile strength and elastic modulus are calculated by the following equations:

$$E_c = V_{f1}E_{f1} + V_{f2}E_{f2} \tag{1a}$$

$$\sigma_c = V_{f1}\sigma_{f1} + V_{f2}\sigma_{f2} \tag{1b}$$

Where, σ and E are the tensile strength and elastic modulus, V is the volume fraction, and the subscripts c and f represent of the composite and fiber, respectively. There are two kinds of fiber in the present study, the subscripts 1 and 2 are used to describe flax and basalt fibers, and $V_f = V_1 + V_2$.

The predicted strength and modulus of HFRP are shown in table 3.

	Tensile strength (MPa)	Elastic modulus(GPa)
Tested	613.1	54.9
Predicted	606.2	55.6

Table 3: Tested and predicted tensile properties of HFRP.

The tested strength and elastic modulus are closed to the calculated results. The deviation between tested and predicted results is 1.1% for tensile strength and 1.3% for modulus. This suggests that in general a good agreement is found between the experimental results and model predictions.

3.2 Compression properties of concrete cylinders

Fig. 3 shows the failure mode of SCC filled FFRP and HFRP tubes. All the cylinders failed with a large deformation and the composites are broken gradually to failure with increasing volume.

Figure 3: Typical failure mode of SCC filled FFRP and HFRP tubular columns.

As is shown in Fig. 4, the stress-strain curves exhibit two stages similar to that of synthetic FRPs confined concrete. When the axial stress is less than the rupture stress of the unconfined concrete, the stress grows linearly as the strain increases. The tangent slope of the stress-strain curve of SCC filled concrete cylinders at the first stage is almost the same as that of plain concrete. According to ACI 440.2R-08, the shapes of the compressive axial stress-strain curves of all the cylinders are close to the heavily confined-hardening ones.

Figure 4: The compressive curve of PC and SCC filled FRP tubes.

The compressive results of SCC filled FRP tubes are shown in Table 4. The compressive efficiency was evaluated following the method of Lam and Teng [5] and Dai et al. [6]. The confinement effectiveness can be calculated with Eq. 2:

$$f_{cu}/f_{co} = 1 + k * f_{i,a}/f_{co} \quad (2)$$

where k is defined as the coefficient of confinements and generally is 3.3 for CFRP strengthened concrete, f_{cu} , f_{co} and $f_{i,a}$ stand for the ultimate stress of the confined, unconfined cylinders and actual confinement respectively, ε_{cu} and ε_{co} mean the ultimate strain of confined and unconfined cylinder. The equation to calculate $f_{i,a}$ recommended by Lam and Teng [7] is given by:

$$f_{i,a} = 2E_{frp}t\varepsilon_{h,rup}/d \quad (3)$$

where E_{frp} , $\varepsilon_{h,rup}$, t are the elastic modulus got from FRP coupon test, ultimate hoop strain and thickness of the wrapped material, d is the diameter of the cylinder.

The ultimate stress and strain at axial and hoop directions of all the cylinders are improved impactful. The confinement effectiveness of SCC filled FFRP and HFRP tubes are more than BFRP tubes which is similar to other synthesis FRPs.

In the present study, 3 design oriented models are adopted to fit the compressive stress-strain curve of SCC filled FFRP/HFRP tubes. The model of Lam and Teng [5] is generally accepted and adopted in ACI 440.2R-08.

$$\sigma_c = (E_c - E_2)^2 * \varepsilon_c^2 \quad \text{for } 0 \leq \varepsilon_c < \varepsilon_t \quad (4a)$$

$$\sigma_c = f_{co} + E_2 \varepsilon_c \quad \text{for } \varepsilon_t \leq \varepsilon_c < \varepsilon_{cu} \quad (4b)$$

where σ_c and ε_c are the compressive stress and strain of SCC filled FFRP and HFRP tubes, f_{co} is the compressive strength of unconfined cylinder. As this model divides the strain-stress curve into two parts, E_c and E_2 are the elastic modulus of confined cylinder at the first and second stage, and $E_c = 4736 * f_{co}^{0.5}$. And ε_t is the strain point where the parabolic first portion meets the linear second portion with a smooth transition, $f_{l,a}$ is calculated by Eq. 3.

	Ultimate stress (MPa)	Ultimate axial stain at break ε_{cu} (%)	Ultimate hoop strain at break $\varepsilon_{h,rupt}$ (%)	Efficiency factor $\varepsilon_{cu}/\varepsilon_{frp}$	k
PC	27	0.2	0.28		
FFRP	55.04	1.23	1.17	0.91	4.42
BFRP	86.3	2.98	2.08	1.34	5.52
HFRP	74.61	2.59	0.914	0.89	4.99

Table 4: The compressive properties of PC and SCC filled FRP tubes.

The model proposed by Wang et al.[8] is based on the large scale reinforced concrete cylinders. The formation of the model is shown is Eq. 5.

$$y = (A + Bx^2) / (1 + Bx + x^r) \quad (5)$$

where $A = E_c/E_{co}$, $B = (AX - X^r Y - Y) / (XY - X^2)$, $X = \varepsilon_{cc}/\varepsilon_{co}$, $Y = f_{cc}/f_{co}$, $r = 3.64(f_{ls}/f_{co}) + 1.26(f_{lf}/f_{co})^{-0.14}$, f_{lf} is the lateral confinement pressure provided by the FRP warp and f_{ls} is the lateral confinement pressure provided by the hoop reinforcement, for confined plain concrete, the parameter $f_{ls} = 0$ and $f_{lf} = f_{la}$, other parameters have the same meaning of the model proposed by Lam and Teng.

The model of Dai et al.[9] is based on actively confined concrete and can be applied to FRP with large rupture strain (LRS), and is shown in Eq. 6.

$$\sigma_c/f_{cc} = (\varepsilon_c/\varepsilon_{cc})^m / [m - 1 + (\varepsilon_c/\varepsilon_{cc})^m] \quad (6a)$$

$$m = E_c / [E_c - f_{cu}/\varepsilon_{cc}] \quad (6b)$$

where the parameters are defined in previous models.

The fitting curves with the models mentioned above are shown in Fig. 5 compared with experimental results. The calculated curves of SCC filled FFRP tubes with the model of Dai are close to test result. The fitting curve of the model proposed by Wang et al. can fit the test results of SCC filled BFRP tubes. The differences of the first part are normal for SCC filled tubes [10]. For specimens with HFRP, the test result is between the fitting curves calculated by the model of Dai et al.[9] and Wang et al.[8]

Figure 5: The fitting curves of SCC filled FFRP, BFRP and HFRP tubes.

The reasons account for the difference between SCC filled FFRP/HFRP and BFRP tubes are the tensile properties of the flax FRP. Similar to the synthesis FRP confined cylinders, SCC filled BFRP tubes are passive and the confining pressure increases due to the expansion of the concrete core. The volume of FFRP will expand during tensile test. Therefore the confining pressure of SCC filled FFRP tube is nonlinear and more than calculated with the expansion of FFRP. Thus the compressive curve of SCC filled FFRP tubes shows more agreements with the actively confined models which is also applicable to large rupture strain (LRS) materials. The experimental compressive stress-strain curve of SCC filled HFRP tube is located between the fitting curves with Dai and Wang's models. That means the confining pressure provided by HFRP mainly depends on the tensile properties of the FRP composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the tensile properties of FFRP, BFRP, HFRP plates and compressive performances of SCC filled those three kinds of FRP tubes are investigated. The following conclusions are drawn from this work. FFRP plates exhibit a nonlinear tensile stress-strain response, which is contrast to BFRP and HFRP. Hybrid of flax fibers with basalt fibers brings in increased tensile properties compared to FFRP. FFRP tubes confines the concrete cylinders effectively, leading to a remarkable enhancement of the compressive stress and strain. The confinement effectiveness of the FFRP and HFRP tubes are greater than that of BFRP.

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